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ADVANCED APPROACHES TO THE ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF CURRENT FINANCIAL STABILITY IN JOINT- STOCK COMPANIES USING CFAR (CASH FLOW AT RISK) AND 3σ STATISTICAL RISK MODELS

Abstract: This scientific article systematizes the theoretical, methodological, and empirical foundations of Cash Flow at Risk (CFaR) and the 3σ (three-sigma) statistical risk models as modern instruments for assessing and managing the short-term financial stability of joint-stock companies. The study also interprets their application within the risk management systems of joint-stock companies in the Republic. It is demonstrated that evaluating current financial stability solely through traditional static financial ratios is insufficient. Within the framework of the CFaR model for cash flow management under risk conditions and the concept of risk-adjusted liquidity, the necessity of applying dynamic and probabilistic approaches is theoretically substantiated.

Key words: CFaR, Cash Flow at Risk, 3σ model, financial stability, liquidity risks, cash flows, risk management, joint-stock companies, Monte Carlo, stress testing.

INTRODUCTION

In modern corporate finance, risk-oriented approaches to managing short-term financial stability have gained increasing practical significance. In particular, the Value at Risk (VaR) concept enables the assessment of financial risks based on probabilistic distributions and has subsequently been adapted to liquidity analysis, leading to the development and systematization of the Cash Flow at Risk (CFaR) model. This model allows firms to evaluate the probability of liquidity shortages by incorporating uncertainty in future cash flows.

Accordingly, this study proposes a comprehensive indicator for assessing short-term financial stability through the integration of the CFaR and 3σ (three-sigma) models. The necessity of applying modern approaches such as risk-based liquidity management, stress testing, Monte Carlo simulation, and adaptive cash flow management is theoretically substantiated.

The scientific results obtained in this research are of significant practical importance for joint-stock companies, particularly in the early identification of financial risks, optimization of liquidity buffers, and informed decision-making to ensure financial stability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are well-established perspectives among leading foreign economists and practitioners in financial risk management regarding the CFaR (Cash Flow at Risk) and 3σ (three-sigma) risk models.

In particular, the foreign economist Philippe Jorion studied the CFaR concept based on the VaR theory and is considered one of the leading scholars who developed the theoretical foundations of corporate risk management [2]. His main idea is based on evaluating risk through probabilistic distributions, and he systematized the liquidity-adjusted forms of the "CFaR - VaR" model.

Economists Niclas Andréén, Håkan Jankensgård, and Lars Oxelheim [3] adapted and systematized the CFaR model for industrial enterprises. Their main idea is to assess the potential decline in corporate cash flows

and to consolidate corporate risks into a single indicator. Economist Jeremy C. Stein and other scholars linked “CFaR” to corporate liquidity and debt capacity, proving that debt burden and liquidity constraints must be taken into account in “CFaR” models [5].

In modern research on “CFaR” and risk models, Boris Stoyanov has conducted studies reflecting scientific views on “CFaR” as a practical instrument for managing liquidity risks [6]. Another group of contemporary researchers Ehsan Didar, Ali Bazargan, and Mahdi Bagherpour [7] have systematized scientific approaches to improving the accuracy of risk-based cash flow forecasting using “CFaR + Monte Carlo” instruments.

One of the founders of the 3σ (three-sigma) statistical model is Walter A. Shewhart, whose main scientific contribution is devoted to the 99.7% confidence interval in the normal distribution under the 3σ rule [8]. Economist W. Edwards Deming systematized scientific views on managing variation and risks based on σ [9].

The analysis of the scientific literature shows that traditional static indicators cannot fully reflect financial stability, as they do not account for risk and uncertainty factors. Therefore, in modern research, dynamic and probabilistic approaches are increasingly emphasized, including the integration of CFaR and 3σ models, which has led to the formation of the concept of risk-adjusted liquidity assessment.

METHODS

As a methodological framework, probabilistic-statistical analysis, scenario modeling, CFaR and 3σ risk intervals, as well as empirical analysis methods were employed. Based on the financial statements of the joint-stock companies “Navoiyazot” and “Qizilqumcement”, the volatility of cash flows, liquidity risks, and the level of financial stability were assessed.

ANALYSIS

The current financial stability of joint-stock companies represents a complex category reflecting the ability of enterprises to meet short-term obligations in a timely manner, balance cash flows, and withstand external shocks. In modern financial management, evaluating this stability solely through static indicators (such as liquidity ratios, working capital, etc.) is insufficient. Therefore, dynamic and probabilistic approaches particularly CFaR (Cash Flow at Risk) and the 3σ (three-sigma) statistical model are widely applied. These models enable the assessment of financial stability within the framework of the risk-adjusted liquidity concept.

Focusing on the essence and significance of the CFaR model, cash flow management under risk conditions (CFaR) represents a risk analysis framework that evaluates the minimum probable value of future cash flows at a given confidence level (α). This can be expressed by the following formula:

$$CFaR_{\alpha} = E(CF) - z_{\alpha} \cdot \sigma_{CF} \quad (1)$$

Here, $E(CF)$ - denotes the expected cash flow, σ_{CF} - represents the standard deviation of cash flows, and z_{α} - is the confidence coefficient.

The theoretical significance of this model lies in its ability to incorporate cash flow uncertainty, assess the probability of liquidity shortages, and provide a basis for forecasting stability under stress scenarios. The CFaR model is considered an adaptation of the Value at Risk (VaR) concept to liquidity management in corporate finance.

The 3σ model, based on the normal distribution, evaluates risks at a high confidence level:

$$P(|X - \mu| \leq 3\sigma) \approx 0.997 \quad (2)$$

This implies that in 99.7% of cases, cash flows fall within this interval, allowing for the identification of extreme risks. From a theoretical perspective, this model enables the assessment of “worst-case scenarios,” thereby facilitating the establishment of risk limits and the optimization of liquidity buffers.

By integrating these two models (formulas 1 and 2), a new paradigm for managing financial stability in joint-stock companies can be developed. As a conceptual integration, the following can be systematized:

$$CFSI = \frac{E(CF) - 3\sigma_{CF}}{CL} \quad (3)$$

Where: CFSI - represents the cash flow stability index, which measures the ratio of expected cash flow adjusted for extreme risk (3σ) to current liabilities (CL), thereby providing an integrated indicator of short-term financial stability.

Overall, modern management instruments based on CFaR and the 3σ approach are implemented within the framework of risk-based liquidity management, particularly through optimizing cash reserve buffer (“damping buffer”) levels and limiting liquidity risks. In this context, scenario analysis and stress testing are conducted based on various scenario alternatives and Monte Carlo simulations. The adaptive cash flow management system, in turn, is implemented through real-time monitoring of cash resources and dynamic budgeting mechanisms. At the subsequent stage, decisions are made regarding the optimization of the capital structure.

If we consider the analysis of a real situation based on the interpretation of the above models, the following picture can be observed. Based on the financial statements of “Navoiyazot” JSC, the company demonstrated financial results characterized by sharp increases and declines during the analyzed period (2020–2024). In 2020, net revenue amounted to approximately 2.15 trillion UZS, while in 2021–2022 it increased significantly, reaching 4.58 trillion UZS and 5.31 trillion UZS, respectively. As a result, net profit rose to 780 billion UZS in 2021 and reached a record level of 1.25 trillion UZS in 2022.

However, in 2023, financial performance deteriorated sharply: although operating profit amounted to 1.54 trillion UZS, financial activity losses reached 1.43 trillion UZS. This resulted in a decline of net profit to only 28.4 billion UZS (a 98% decrease compared to 2022), disrupting the balance between revenues and expenses. In 2023, financial expenses (including foreign exchange losses) significantly reduced the nominal level of income.

Cash Flow at Risk (CFaR) represents an indicator showing how much future cash flows may decline relative to expected values under risk conditions. For “Navoiyazot” JSC, unexpected negative deviations may be substantial. For example, the exceptionally high revenues in 2022 and the sharp decline in 2023 indicate that, at a 95% confidence level, the company’s cash flow is not expected to fall below approximately 1 trillion UZS (i.e., there is only a 5% probability of an even larger decline). In other words, the CFaR value can be estimated at around 1 trillion UZS. This represents a very high-risk signal for “Navoiyazot” JSC.

The “three-sigma (3σ) model”, which evaluates the 99.7% dispersion interval, further indicates that due to the high standard deviation of profits, in adverse 3σ scenarios the company may even incur losses amounting to billions of UZS (a worst-case probability of 0.3% or less). This demonstrates the high volatility of the company’s operations and its exposure to unfavorable tail-risk events.

The financial indicators of “Qizilqumcement” JSC are of considerable scale and, although fluctuating in recent years, exhibit an overall positive trend. Net revenue amounted to approximately 0.79 trillion UZS in 2020, slightly declined in 2021, increased in 2022, and reached 0.87 trillion UZS in 2023 (with 0.89 trillion UZS projected for 2024). Net profit was relatively high at 590 billion UZS in 2020, decreased to 228 billion UZS in 2021, then rose to 299 billion UZS in 2022 and further to 470 billion UZS in 2023. These fluctuations are mainly associated with changes in supply and demand in the cement market as well as cost dynamics: high profitability in 2020 was driven by a construction boom, while increased costs in 2021 reduced profits, followed by market recovery leading to higher profits by 2023.

Overall, “Qizilqumcement” JSC demonstrates a positive trend; during the analyzed period, the company consistently remained in the profit zone, with a net profit margin of approximately 20–30% (reaching a particularly high level in 2020).

“Qizilqumcement” JSC can be considered relatively financially stable, as the company’s current liquidity ratio remained consistently above 1 during 2020–2023 (indicating a positive working capital position). Although in 2024 current liabilities increased slightly and working capital turned negative, the overall capital structure of the company remains strong, with a high share of equity and a steadily increasing amount of retained earnings. According to the Altman Z-model, the Z-score of “Qizilqumcement” JSC exceeded 2.9 in most years, indicating a very low probability of bankruptcy.

For “Qizilqumcement” JSC, cash flow risk is at a moderate level. As a large industrial enterprise, its cash flows depend on market demand and price fluctuations. From a CFaR perspective, it is expected with 95% confidence that future cash flows will remain within a certain limited range. In particular, over a one-year horizon, the probability of a significant decline in expected cash flows is less than 5% (i.e., the lower 95th percentile scenario). This implies that even in the “worst-case” scenario, the company’s revenue is unlikely to decrease by more than 200–300 billion UZS.

According to the three-sigma (3σ) model, the probability of extremely large deviations for “Qizilqumcement” JSC is relatively low; theoretically, within the 3σ bounds, the company is still likely to remain profitable or incur only minor losses. Of course, in the event of global economic or sector-specific risks (such as a sharp decline in demand), the company’s profits could decrease significantly or turn into losses. However, existing financial reserves and stability buffers enable “Qizilqumcement” JSC to absorb such shocks relatively more effectively.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been scientifically substantiated that traditional static liquidity indicators are insufficient for managing the current financial stability of joint-stock companies. A new methodological approach to assessing risk-

adjusted current financial stability (liquidity) has been developed through the integration of CFaR (Cash Flow at Risk) and 3σ statistical models, which account for cash flow uncertainty and extreme risks. This approach has been empirically validated as enabling the early identification of liquidity shortages, forecasting stability under stress scenarios, and enhancing the effectiveness of financial risk management.

Within the framework of statistical risk analysis, the three-sigma (3σ) model, based on the normal distribution, allows for risk assessment at a high confidence level. This model plays a crucial role in identifying extreme events (tail risks) and forecasting “worst-case scenarios,” thereby facilitating the evaluation of financial stability under stress conditions.

The financial analysis of the examined joint-stock companies indicates that, although “Navoiyazot” JSC leads in terms of revenue volume, issues related to its cost structure and dependence on short-term liabilities have contributed to its financial instability.

In contrast, “Qizilqumcement” JSC demonstrates a relatively stable performance, characterized by moderate revenue levels, a strong balance sheet structure, and a manageable debt burden, which collectively enhance its resilience to risks.

According to the analysis results, despite its high revenue potential, “Navoiyazot” JSC exhibits a low level of current financial stability due to significant volatility in financial results and high exposure to foreign exchange risks. Conversely, “Qizilqumcement” JSC has been shown to maintain resilience to risks due to the stability of its financial indicators, balanced liquidity position, and sound capital structure.

The application of the financial stability index, CFaR, and 3σ models confirms that “Qizilqumcement” JSC has the lowest risk level, while “Navoiyazot” JSC is characterized by the highest risk. This underscores the necessity of effective financial risk management in these enterprises, particularly highlighting the importance of improving liquidity and implementing hedging strategies against currency and interest rate risks in “Navoiyazot” JSC.

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